

THE EFFECT OF COMMODITY PRICE CHANGES ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF OIL FIRMS

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Abstract: *Prices of oil and gas are generally known to be highly volatile and the recent price changes have caused several concerns for consumers, corporations and countries alike as they experience high dependency on oil and gas for transportation, electricity generation and industrial production. The specific objective of the study was to investigate commodity price changes effect on financial performance of the oil and gas sector. In so doing, data was sourced from active oil and gas firms quoted in the African Stock market. Panel data regression using Hausman's fixed effect and random effect models was adopted. However, the study also conducted other diagnostic tests like multicollinearity test using Variance inflation factor, Heteroscedasticity test, correlation analysis. Findings showed that Commodity price change has negative but statistically significant effect on the financial performance of the African listed oil and gas firms at 1% level and that more profits were made during the period of fall in price of commodities, possibly because of higher demand in quantity, but lesser profit when prices rise, as a result of low demand associated with high prices. The study concludes that commodity price changes have strong influence on determination of the financial performance of oil firms and recommends that management should have adequate storage facilities to be able to store up more products when price falls. This would enable them sell more quantities at a lower price when price rises.*

Key words: *commodity price changes, financial performance, oil and gas, firms, African Stock Market.*

INTRODUCTION

Oil is a fundamental input into the world economy because it is a primary source of energy in the industrial, electrical, and transport sectors. Extreme oil price movements are partially responsible for the recessions faced by Nigeria and other African countries in recent time and these extreme movements in oil prices influence the economic activity and significantly affect movements in the stock market. Thus, the performance of the oil and gas sector goes a long way in determining the

intermediation process of the economy's financial performance (Oladejo & Oladipo, 2011). Financial performance can be measured in terms of profitability, liquidity and firms' value. The relevance of the financial performance of the oil and gas sector to the socio-economic development of a nation leads to the Nigerian government commitment to the effectiveness of this sector of the economy over the years. As a result of this, the continuous existence of the sector is therefore a crucial issue to every stakeholder. For this sector of the economy to function well, it is imperative that a good governance policy be put in place in order to ensure the smooth operation of the oil and gas sector in the world today.

Prices of oil and gas are generally known to be highly volatile (Pindyck, 2001; Hamilton, 2009), and the recent price changes have caused several concerns for consumers, corporations and countries alike as they experience high dependency on oil and gas for transportation, electricity generation and industrial production. To better understand these price fluctuations, several authors including Ozuomba, Nwadiakor and Anichebe (2019), Alquist and Kilian (2010), have studied risk forecasting models for the price of crude oil, with varying success. The price of oil has since increased together with the increase in demand from emerging markets like China and India.

Nigeria is the economic driving force in West Africa because of its richness in fossil fuel that in turn plays a major impact in revenue generation in the country. Since the removal of fuel subsidy in 2012 that led to the increase of pump prices, oil prices and their high volatility have generated significant concern for consumers, producers, and governments, as well as a growing academic interest in studying this important economic variable of changes in commodity prices. Several factors affect the oil price, the main ones being the policies of the Organization of the Petroleum Exporting Countries (OPEC), military conflicts, geopolitical tensions, natural disasters, imbalances between supply and demand in international markets, among others.

The likes of Oyerogba and Ogunlde (2016) looked at links between financial sectors in selected African Countries, Ekinici (2016) studied same in Turkey, however, since it is obvious that oil and gas sectors in African countries are alike and are indispensable sectors of the economy, it becomes imperative therefore to conduct studies on how commodity price changes have influenced the financial performances of oil and gas industry in the African Stock Market. The following hypothesis was formulated;

Ho₁: Commodity price changes do not have significant effect on the financial performance of oil firms in the African stock market.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This study is anchored on Arbitrage Pricing Theory (APT) developed by Ross (1976) it is a one-period model in which every investor believes that the stochastic properties of returns on capital assets are consistent with a factor structure. Ross argues that if equilibrium prices offer no arbitrage opportunities over static portfolios of the assets, then the expected returns on the assets are approximately linearly related to the factor loadings. (The factor loadings, or betas, are proportional to the returns' co-

variances with the factors.) The model is used to identify the mispriced assets. It has three major assumptions; that: capital markets are perfectly competitive; Investors always prefer more wealth to less wealth with certainty; the stochastic process generating asset returns can be expressed as a linear function of a set of K risk factors (or indexes), and all unsystematic risk is diversified away. In an efficient market, return differentials should not occur, meaning that either the markets are not efficient for extended periods of time or the market prices are efficient.

Commodity Price Changes

Commodity prices are prices of oil per barrel as agreed by OPEC Countries. Commodities are reasonably interchangeable goods or material bought and sold freely as articles of commerce which includes agricultural products, fuels and metals that are traded in bulk on a commodity exchange or spot market (usinessdictionary.com). Ildirar and Iscan (2016) opine that commodities consist of the basic materials and natural resources used in virtually all products manufacturing process, notably among them are oil, wheat, iron and robber that are the main components of many common goods in our lives.

Review of related literature on commodity prices were carried out by some by; Farooki and Kaplinsky (2012) who classified commodities into industrial crops ((Timber), Fisheries, and Cereals, Beverages, and Livestock, Precious metals, Coal and Petroleum products. The price changes of the most important commodities in the world's commodity exchange markets influence the price of local producers or imported productions. Norhafiza, Sabariah & Rusmawati (2014). evaluated the effect of commodity prices (crude oil, coal, crude palm oil, gold nickel and tin), exchange rate and investment on the firms' value, either directly or indirectly through mediation of business risk. The study covers a sample of 25 mining and agricultural firms listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange spanning through 2010 to 2014 that gives a panel balanced data of 5 years, which generated 125 observations. The result indicate that oil prices and exchange rate affect the firms value either directly or indirectly though business risk as mediation variable, but risk does not mediate the effect of the investment on the firms' value.

Bagirov and Mateus (2017) expanded the understanding of the relationship between oil prices, stock markets and firm performance on Europe stock. Their study was in three stages; firstly, they investigated the effect of oil price and Stop Market in Europe. Their results indicate the presence of one directional relationship between oil and most of the European markets. More so the results show spillovers volatility between returns in oil price and stock markets. Crude oil price has significant positive impact on the performance of listed oil and gas firm in Western Europe. Similarly, Alao and Oloni (2015) investigated the effects of commodity price changes on firm's value of Drink service industry on the stock exchange market in selected African Countries. Using descriptive survey design, they collected secondary data from 11 firms on food and drink sector from 2009 to 2013. They found that the commodity prices indicators have positive and significant relationship with firm value which was represented by revenue, cost of sales and stock prices.

Financial Performance:

Financial performance is a business operation activity to determine how economically well or profitable the business has done within a particular period. Financial performance is the extent to which financial goals or obligation of a firm is being accomplished. More so, Return on Assets (ROA) and return on Equity (ROE) ratios are the two key financial performance indicators commonly used to measure firms' performance quite effectively.

METHODOLOGY

The research design of expo facto (after the event) was adopted considering the specific objectives and the panel statistical technique that were applied. This study covered active quoted oil and gas firms in the African stock market for a period of ten years starting from 2013 to 2022. This period provoked the study because of the economic depression witnessed generally in the world economy within the period, especially the outbreak of covid-19 pandemic. Secondary data were used since studies have proven the validity and reliability of the empirical result using secondary data. The population of this study consisted of the 10 active quoted oil and gas firms in the African Stock market as at 31st December 2022. The active quoted oil and gas firms as at 31st December 2022 are as follows:

S/N	Oil and gas firms	country
1	African Clean Energy Solution (ACES.mu)	Mauritius
2	Conoil Nigeria plc (CONOIL.ng)	Nigeria
3	Eterna Nigeria plc (ETERNA.ng)	Nigeria
4	MRS oil Nigeria plc (MRS.ng)	Nigeria
5	Seplat Energy Marketing Nigeria plc (SEPLAT.ng)	Nigeria
6	Total Energy Marketing plc (TOTAL.ng)	Nigeria
7	Swala oil and gas (SWALA.tz)	Tanzania
8	Tol gases ltd (TOL.tz)	Tanzania
9	Umeme ltd (UMEME.ug)	Uganda
10	Puma Energy Zambia plc (PUMA.zm)	Zambia

Source: African Stock Market, 2023

Panel data regression using fixed effect and random effect models was adopted in order to control for individual unobserved heterogeneity, obtain more accurate results (Temple, 1999; Woodridge, 2002; and Hsiao, 2003 as cited in Alajekwu, 2018). Cross-sectional and time series data are pooled in the regression to overcome the problem of insufficient degree of freedom. However, the study also conducted other diagnostic tests like multicollinearity test using Variance inflation factor, which checked if the independent variables of the study were highly correlated among themselves; Heteroscedasticity test, which checked for the presence of an outlier or whether the residual of the error term is constant and variable omission test that checked if the model was miss-specified.

Decision rule for regression analysis: It is interpreted as the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that is predictable from the independent variable. Its decision rule is +1 or -1.

Model: Return on Assets (ROA) model: tested as stand-alone variables.

$ROA = F (COMP, FS, FA)$

$ROA = \alpha + \beta_1 COMP_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots equ (1).$

Where:

B_1 = Coefficient of Proxy of independent variable

ROA = an indicator representing return on asset (proxy for dependent variable).

COMP = commodity price

e = Error term

i = firm

t = time

Apriori expectations: $B_1, > 0$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive statistics

The descriptive statistics result provides evidence on the mean distribution, maximum, minimum, standard deviation, median and the count of the data collected which span from 2013 to 2022. The result is presented thus;

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Return on assets (ROA) has a mean of 0.7078 with maximum and minimum values of 18.45 and -19.450 respectively. The values indicated that wide variation exists among the oil firms in their earning potentials across the nations as the standard deviation is higher than the mean value. The other variable commodity price (COMPR) shows average value of 63.88 US dollar, with maximum value of \$ 97.98 and minimum value of \$39.68. The standard deviation of 20.06 that is lower than the mean value invariably shows that the values clustered around the mean, therefore are not dispersed.

Test for Normality of Residua

The assumption to make when testing for normality residua is that “sample distribution is normal”. Hence, the distribution is not normal if the test is significant at 5% or 1% level. This study adopted the Shapiro-Wilk test for normality of residua test procedure for $n = 10$ to $n = 2000$ this is in line with the position of Razali and Wah (2011). Consequently, the study conducted the test for normality of residua as shown in the table below:

Table 2: Shapiro-Wilk W test for normal data

The normality results in table 2 above shows that the joint probability of $ROA = 0.000$ and $COMPR = 0.000$ are not normally distributed since their joint probability value is less than or equal to 5% critical value. These results were obtained from the probability z statistics as revealed in the above

table. Following this finding, the study shall continue with non-parametric approach to testing the relationship among the variables, using Spearman correlation.

Analysis

With non-normal data which the normality of residua test result reveals, alternatives to the Pearson approach might be justified. The robustness of Spearman's versus Pearson's test has received relatively less empirical scrutiny. In one of the few studies, Fowler (1987) found that Spearman's r was more powerful than Pearson's r across a range of non-normal bivariate distributions. The power benefit of Spearman's r may be the result of rank-ordering causing outliers to contract toward the centre of the distribution (Gauthier, 2001). Upon this understanding and based on the fact that the data set followed a non-normal distribution, the study employs the Spearman Rank Correlation technique to conduct the possible association between the variables of interest shown in the table below;

Table 3: Correlation Matrix Analyses

Specifically, the analysis from the spearman rank correlation showed that commodity price (-0.0063) has negative and low correlation with return on assets of the oil firms listed on the African stock market for the period covered. The result did not indicate any high correlation among the independent variable. However, the study shall engage variance inflation factor to test properly whether high collinearity problems exist.

Table 4 Multicollinearity Test using Variance Inflation Factor

The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) statistics as presented above was used to ascertain the presence of multicollinearity. The decision rule being that VIF-statistic above ten (10) indicates multicollinearity, otherwise it does not give cause of concern and it is observed that the variables have VIF's values more than 10 and hence there is no serious indication of multicollinearity.

Constant Variance

The variance of error term is expected to be constant for each observation or a range of observations which is known as homoscedasticity. Whenever a change occurs on the variance, it tends to reduce the precision of the estimation in ordinary least square (OLS) linear regression. Hence, the study used the Breusch-pagan/ Cook-Waisberg test for the heteroscedasticity of the residuals as presented in the table below.

Table 5 Heteroskedasticity Test

Heteroscedasticity test has a decision rule that there is no heteroscedasticity if the probability of F value is greater than the critical value was at 5% level. The table 5 above indicates that probability value of 0.0000 is less than the critical value of 0.05. Therefore, we conclude that there is heteroscedasticity, which means there is no constant variance.

Table 6 Hausman Test

The Hausman test shows a P value (0.6003) that is higher than 5% critical value which is an indication that random effect result is better than fixed effect result, therefore we concludes to use random effect

result for making inferences. More so, random effect panel regression technique has the capacity to redress the absence of homoscedasticity.

Panel Regression Analysis

The study employed panel regression analysis to ascertain the cause and effect links between our explanatory variables and the dependent variable, as well as used this analysis for testing the formulated hypotheses. The summarized results of the panel regression analysis are presented in the table below.

Table 7 - Summary of Regression Estimation

From table 7 above, it is seen that the F-statistics and its corresponding P-value were 19.31(0.0001) and 17.70(0.000) for random effect model and fixed effect model respectively. This shows that the model is valid for drawing inference since it is statistically significant at 1% levels. The R-squares (i.e. the regression coefficient) were shown as 0.3955 and 0.6269 for random effect model and fixed effect model respectively. This value indicates that 39.6% and 62.7% of the systematic variations in firm financial performance, measured with return on assets (ROA) is explained by the explanatory variable used for random effect and fixed effect models respectively.

The fixed effect panel regression estimation was based on the assumption of no correlation between the error term and the independent variable, whereas the model of the random effect is performed on the bases that the error term and the independent variable are correlated. Put differently, Random Effects models have the capacity to correct for omitted variable bias, and presence of autocorrelation and heteroscedasticity in panel data. Therefore, it will provide a remedy to variable specification error and heteroscedasticity problems found in the study data.

However, it is a convention to introduce a mechanism that will help make a choice between the two-panel regression estimator (fixed effect model and random effect model) to rely on. The Hausman Test was used as that mechanism. It is a rule of the Hausman Test to assume that Random Effect result is better applied to fixed effect result on the null hypothesis. The probability of the Hausman Test is 0.6003, which implies non-significant at 5% level. Therefore, the study accepts null hypothesis and by the standard of Hausman Test, random effect panel regression result is more appealing for the discussion and for making inferences. To this end, the study applied random effect result in testing its hypotheses as presented below.

Hypothesis 1: Commodity price changes do not have significant on the financial performance of oil firms in the African stock market.

The random effect regression results obtained from the ROA model revealed that commodity price has a significant effect on financial performance (ROA) of oil firms listed on African stock market during the period under investigation. This finding is seen from the statistics presented where commodity price (COMPR) possesses the values (Coef. = -0.715, z = -2.29, and p- value = 0.022). The negative coefficient indicates that commodity price has inverse effect on financial performance of oil firm on African

market. The z-statistics and p-value that is less than 5% critical value show that commodity price is significantly affecting ROA. More so, the negative association between commodity price and financial performance of the oil firms shows that increase in commodity price would deplete the value of ROA of the firms. In which case, rise in the commodity price by one unit would cause a 2.29-unit reduction on the financial performance (ROA) of oil firms listed on the African stock market. Hence, the study affirms that alternate hypothesis that commodity price has statistically significant effect on financial performance of oil and gas firms on African stock market.

FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study found out that Commodity price change has negative but statistically significant effect on the financial performance of the African listed oil and gas firms at 1% level. The study therefore, concludes that commodity price changes have strong influence on determination of the financial performance of the oil and gas firms on African stock market. More importantly, it recommends that management should have adequate storage facilities to be able to store up more than enough products when price falls. This would enable them sell more quantities at a lower price when price rises. The result shows that more profits were made during the period of fall in price of commodities, possibly because of higher demand in quantity, but lesser profit when prices rise, may be because of low demand associated with high prices. Therefore, having enough storage could help them explore more profit during the periods of rise in price.

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APPENDICES

Table I: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
ROA	79	.7078377	26.4026	-19.45	18.45
COMPR	80	63.87713	20.06161	39.68	97.98

Source: Stata 2014 output

Table II: Shapiro-Wilk W test for normal data

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
ROA	79	0.34032	44.816	8.326	0.00000
COMPR	80	0.89905	6.929	4.241	0.00001

Source: Stata 14 output

Table III: Correlation Matrix Analyses

Key			
rho			
Sig. level			
	ROA	COMPR	EQP
ROA	1.0000		
COMPR	-0.0063	0.0290	1.0000
	0.9579	0.2401	0.8087

Source: Stata 14 output

Specifically, the analysis from the spearman rank correlation showed that commodity price (-0.0063) has negative and low correlation with return on assets of the oil firms listed on the African stock market for the period covered. The result did not indicate any high correlation among the independent variable. However, the study shall engage variance inflation factor to test properly whether high collinearity problems exist.

Table IV: Multicollinearity Test using Variance Inflation Factor

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
COMPR	1.66	0.350151
Mean VIF	2.61	

Table V: Heteroskedasticity Test

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

Ho: Constant variance

Variables: fitted values of ROA

chi2(1) = 32.64

Prob >chi2 = 0.0000

Source: Stata 14 output

Table VI: Hausman Test

Test: Ho: difference in coefficients not systematic

chi2(12) = (b-B)'[(V_b-V_B)^(-1)](b-B)

= 35.82

Prob>chi2 = 0.6003

Source: Stata 14 output

Table VII - Summary of Regression Estimation

	Random effect result	Fixed effect result
	Coefficient () p-value [] z-stat	Coefficient () p-value [] t-stat
<i>COMPR</i>	-3.715 (0.022) [-2.29]	-0.903 (0.617) [-0.50]
	Random effect result	Fixed effect result
<i>R</i> ²	0.3955	0.6269
<i>Adj R</i> ²	0.3405	0.6168
<i>F-Stat</i>	19.31	17.70
<i>P(f-stat)</i>	0.0001	0.0000
<i>Hausman</i>		0.6003
<i>Ramsey RESET Test</i>		0.000